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THE ROLE OF PERCEIVED ENJOYMENT AND SOCIAL INFLUENCES UPON HOW USERS PARTICIPATE IN AND RESPOND TO ADVERTISING IN ONLINE SOCIAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Present research is an attempt to analyze the role of perceived enjoyment and social influences in response to online social networks' advertisements (OSNs). To this end, the present research model was tested based on data gathered from 390 questionnaires distributed among business management students of Tehran North branch of Islamic Azad University and by applying structural equation modeling and LISEREL software. It was found that there is positive and significant relationship between perceived enjoyment and social influence variables including social identity, group norm, and subjective norm. Results are also indicative of positive relationship between social influence variables and group intentions toward advertising in online social networks. On the other hand, it was found that there is positive and significant relationship between social identity and perceived advertisement relevance. Besides, positive relationship between group intention toward advertising in OSNs and perceived advertising relevance, positive relationship between group intention to advertising in OSNs and perceived advertisement value, and positive relationship between perceived advertisement relevance in OSNs and perceived advertisement value were confirmed and supported. Finally, it was found that there is positive and significant relationship between perceived advertisement value and response to advertisement in OSNs, and also between perceived advertisement relevance in OSNs and response to advertisement.

Keywords: Online Social Networks, Advertisement, Perceived Enjoyment, Social Influences

1. Introduction

Within past decade, online social networks (OSNs) have grown strikingly (Guo et al. 2015). Millions of Internet users throughout the world have visited thousands of social media sites and have taken advantage of free services provided with these sites in order to communicate with their friends and share user-created contents such as; photos, videos, weblogs, etc (Kim et al. 2010). As a matter of fact, online social networks have turned in to an extremely important phenomenon in human communities and have rendered new definition of communication patterns and relationships (Krishnamurthy and Dou 2008). On the other hand, quick development of these networks has pushed advertisers to find new ways for controlling them so as to reach their own advertisement goals (Zeng et al. 2009). Online social networks which initially were mainly social phenomena have captured gradually more and more companies' advertisement investments. In this regard, according to a report, in 2014 over 17 billion dollars were paid on advertisement in online social networks and this figure is predicted to reach to 36 billion dollars in 2017 (emarketer 2015). Though over commercialization of online social networks and consequently reduction of their attractiveness have worried users (Mesure and Griggs 2007, Taylor et al. 2011), the survival of these sites are conditioned to advertisement income.

Factors determining users' reactions to advertisements must be identified and analyzed so that these online social networks change into effective advertisement media. Therefore, this issue has recently attracted many marketing researchers (e.g. Pinho and Soares 2015, Soares and Pinho 2014, Zeng et al. 2009). Many reasons are behind users' intention to online social networks. The most important one is representation of one's public and semi-public profile on social network sites such as Facebook, LinkedIn, My Space, Twitter, etc. creating a list of

users with whom connections are shared, view and cross their connections within the system, or visiting personal profiles of others within the system all are propelling (Boyd and Ellison 2007). Interaction within online social networks can endow users with sense of preciousness and even it is a means through which they can show their real identity (Zhou 2011). Attending in these virtual communities paves the way for establishing new connections between those of similar interests. Subsequently, social influence variables are the basic feature of attending in online social networks. People gain part of their identities from networks by which they connect. They adapt themselves to the group's norms and develop joint objectives (Zeng et al. 2009).

In some circumstances, social networking is merely for pleasure. Online games are directed for example by people who develop social functional programs. Therefore, one must distinguish between utilitarian and hedonic function of Internet and online social networks. While the former is of instrumental value for user, the later, incorporating enjoyment and entertainment, is self actualizing (Van der Heijden 2004). Hence, the present research is initially focused on the impact of perceived enjoyment upon social influence variables including social identity, group norms, and subjective norms. It also seeks to analyze the effect of social influence variables on advertisement related variables such as group intentions towards advertising, perceived advertisement relevance, and perceived advertisement value. Finally, the impact of aforementioned relationships on response towards OSN advertisements is studied. Thus, it will be analyzed how perceived enjoyment of membership in online social networks affects upon their joint identities and norms and how the joint identity and norm of group members propels them to united reaction to advertisements in online social networks.

1. Literature Review

According to Boyd and Ellison (2007), online social network is a web-based service which allows 1- a public or semi-public profile be created within the system borders; 2- a list of other users capable of communicating be made, and 3- others' connections be traced and visited. Although social network sites can have numerous features different from one site to the other, their functions can be divided in to five general areas (Kasavana et al. 2010);

- 1) General : social network sites used for meeting friends and communicating with them, sharing material, programs, and interests (including Facebook, Our Cut, and My Space);
- 2) Practice: a network of experts and practitioners in areas such as computer codes or music (such as Justplainfolks, Plaxo, and LinkedIn);
- 3) Interest: a network of people which is formed around a joint interest including; game, sport, music, stock market, politics, health, financial issues, migration, etc. (such as E-Democracy.Org, Political Discussion Group, Social picks, and Stock Market Site).
- 4) Affinity: a network of people of same identities regarding demographic and geographical characteristics such as women, African Americans, Arab Americans (Ivillage, and Focusing on Women).
- 5) Sponsored: communities which are established by commercial, state, nonprofit organizations and with different aims such as Nike and IBM.

2-1. Perceived Enjoyment

People's motivation for doing a task can originate either from their utilitarian needs (tendency to achieve some practical and functional benefits) or their hedonic needs (experiential need involving emotional responses or fantasies) (Solomon et al. 2014). Thus, the distinction between utilitarian consumption and hedonic consumption plays an important role in understanding consumer's behavior (Hirschman and Holbrook 1982). Utilitarian consumption of Internet has been widely studied. For instance, some studies have investigated about perceived usefulness and found that this concept shows solid relationship with tendency to using technology

(e.g. Davis 1989, Davis et al. 1992). In this research, hedonic aspect is highlighted. Social networks are fun, entertaining, stimulate fantasy and relieve users from stressful life (Van der Heijden 2004).

Perceived enjoyment denotes how much using a particular technology per se and regardless of any functional consequence is perceived enjoyable (Davis et al. 1992, Venkatesh 2000). Some studies are indicative of positive impact of perceived enjoyment on technology acceptance by users (Li 2011, Lin and Lu 2011, Van der Heijden 2004, Venkatesh 2000). It was also found that the more perceived enjoyment, the more the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (Pinho and Soares 2015, Teo and Noyes 2011, Van der Heijden 2004).

2-2. Social Influence

Based on social influence theory, people's conduct is influenced by three social processes including compliance, identification, and internalization (Kelman 1974). Compliance is suggestive of change in one's conduct in order to adapt with ideas of those others who matter to him. Identification implies individual identification within a community for example; having sense of belongingness and attachment. Internalization reflects one's being influenced due to the congruity of their values with those of the group members (Dholakia et al. 2004). Compliance, identification, and internalization are indicative of subjective norm, social identity, and group norm, respectively (Dholakia et al. 2004, Shen et al. 2011).

Subjective norm refers to the impact of others' ideas on user's conduct. When majority of those who matter to the user suggest them to attend in a community, they adapt themselves to view points of others even if they don't have a positive attitude to participation in that society (Zhou 2011). Social identity is identifying people considering their relationship with group so that one regards themselves as a member of a group and feels belonged to it (Dholakia et al. 2004). Social identity is made up of three elements i.e. cognitive, affective, and evaluative (Ellemers et al. 1999). Cognitive social identity entails development of a kind of self awareness through membership in a community which includes similarities with other members of the group and discrepancies with other non-members.

Evaluative social identity implies the value of membership in a group and refers to a sort of evaluation and weighing the value of joining or refraining from a group (Shen et al. 2011). Group norms are a combination of goals, values, beliefs, and rituals which are shared and among group members and they feel committed to them (Postmes et al. 2000). Group norms emerge in groups within a period of time through interaction and relationships and leave consistent and severe effects on ideologies and conduct of group members (Hogg and Terry 2000).

Widespread studies have been carried out about adjustment of social influence theory in the domain of recognizing recognition of online social networks' users. It was demonstrated that all three variables i.e. subjective norm, group norm and social identity affect on user desire and intention (e.g. Shen et al. 2011, Zeng et al. 2009, Zhou 2011).

2-3. Advertisement-Related Variables

As stated earlier, marketers are extremely fond of taking advantage of online social networks. In one hand, these networks resort to advertisement for offering free service to their users (Soares and Pinho 2014). Advertisers can apply their knowledge about specific part of market to design appropriate advertisement since they are aware of the profile and traits of these particular communities. On the other hand, consumers may probably find private and personal contents of online social networks more attractive and take interest in them (Tucker 2014). On the contrary, if they feel their privacy is violated, the same contents may seem not only creepy but off putting (Stone 2010). Therefore, in order not to seclude consumers, balance must be kept. Besides the three constructs, group intentions to accept advertising in OSN, perceived advertisement relevance, and perceived advertisement value were investigated.

Group intentions to accept advertising in OSN: group intention construct drew the attention of social science researchers under the labels such as collective intentions, we-intentions, and shared intentions (Soares and Pinho 2014). Inclination to belong to OSN and participating in it generates a kind of group feeling among members which can motivate them to join to group activities. In this regard, Bagozzi and Dholakia (2002) believe that as long as the values and goals of members are consistent with those of community, their intention will boost. Social networks enable people to create personal profile for themselves, acquaint with familiar and probable friends and follow or visit other members' activities. Consequently, online social networks foster social interactions and make self identity expression and community building possible. As Zeng et al. (2009) states: "online social community members of a strong social identity must be able to internalize this idea more easily that community advertising is essential for preserving that community site".

Advertisement Relevance Perception: advertisement relevance refers to how much advertisement is relevant to a consumer and how helpful it is to aid the consumer in reaching his goals and values (Solomon et al. 2014). Studies demonstrate that relevant advertisement draws more attention and consequently affect on effectiveness of online advertisements (Li and Bukovac 1999). Besides, Campbell and Wright (2008) believe that in an online context, the personal relevance of advertisement is an important factor for showing a user's interest in online interaction. According to Zeng et al., (2009), users of a community accept advertisements of a community providing that they are pertinent to their community themes and those commercial messages which are not their favorite are annoying. Hence, perceived relevance of advertisement has great potential for adapting the content of advertisement with online users' interests.

Perceived advertisement value: advertisement value implies "the overall representation of the worth of advertising to consumers" (Ducoffe 1995) and is regarded as a measure of advertisement effectiveness (Soares and Pinho 2014). According to extant theoretical literature, advertising's ability to supply information is the first drive for its approval by consumers (Bauer and Greyser 1968). It was also found that informative value of advertisements has positive impact upon advertisement value and advertisement can create value for users by providing them with more relevant information (Ducoffe 1996). In an online environment, advertisers can take advantage of what they know about different audiences, especially regarding demographic and psychological characteristics, and design advertisements which create value for users effectively. For example, face book and My Space can address its members' profiles based on categories such as place, sex, age, work place, favorites, etc. Therefore, advertisers can be more efficient for their users by addressing their own market and designing advertisements tailored to an effective value.

2. Research Hypotheses and Conceptual Model

As depicted in chart 1, research hypotheses are based on the impact of perceived enjoyment on social influence variables and the effect of these variables on advertisement related variables in online social networks. In this regard, one of the principle objectives of present study is scrutinizing the relationship between perceived enjoyment and social influence variables. Mzoughi et al. (2010) carried out a research about online gamers and found that perceived enjoyment of attending in small groups consolidates the solidarity of group members. In other words, perceived enjoyment, as a personal experience, can shape social identity, strengthen it, and enable adoption of joint group norms. Furthermore, Soares and Pinho (2014) confirmed the relationship between perceived enjoyment and social influence variables. Therefore, the following hypotheses are stated:

H1: there is a positive relationship between perceived enjoyment and social identity.

H2: there is a positive relationship between perceived enjoyment and group norm.

H3: there is a positive relationship between perceived enjoyment and subjective norm.

As mentioned earlier, when majority of those who matter to a person recommend him/her to join into an activity, he/she will probably accept their suggestion and ideas even if he/she doesn't have a positive attitude to that activity (Zhou 2011). Accordingly, both the theory of reasoned action (TRA) and the theory of planned behavior (TPB) assert that subjective norm influences on behavioral inclination (Ajzen 1991, Fishbein and

Ajzen 1975). This belief was also supported by some other studies (Li et al. 2008, Pavlou and Fygenon 2006). Besides, other studies have reported the significant effects of subjective norm on social network users (Shen et al. 2011, Zhou 2011). On the other hand, the social influence theory claims that individual conduct is influenced by compliance process. Therefore, the forth research hypothesis is as follows;

H4: there is a positive relationship between subjective norm and group intention to accept advertising in online social networks.

Many researchers argue that one's conduct is the result of his/her social interactions. People can expand the depth, width, and efficiency of their mutual understanding through close and intimate social interactions (Chiu et al. 2006, Lane and Lubatkin 1998). Zeng et al., (2009) argue that "when online social network members share a strong group benefit norm, they must have more tangible intention to accept advertising". According to studies, once strong group benefit norm is formed, members will be sure that they are following a joint goal. Hence, the probability of developing joint intentions among them will enhance (Dholakia et al., 2004). On the other hand, several studies have confirmed the relationship between group norm and users' intention to participate in online social networks (Soares and Pinho 2014, Zeng et al. 2009, Zhou 2011). Consequently, the fifth research hypothesis is as follows;

H5: there is positive relationship between group norm and group intention to accept advertising in online social networks.

Members of an OSN can be classified base on the solidarity of their interdependence i.e. based on a combination of their time, severity of emotions, intimacy, and reciprocity (Granovetter 1973). Thus, it can be expected that social identities of an OSN impact on group intentions to accept advertising which is related to that group favorites. On the other hand, some studies have approved the relationship between social identity and users' intention to participate in online social networks (Solomon et al. 2014, Zeng et al. 2009, Zhou 2011). Thus, the sixth research hypothesis is as follows;

H6: there is a positive relationship between social identity and group intention to accept advertising in online social networks.

When members of a group shape a strong group identity, they expect more of content related to their community as the symbol of their community identity; that advertisements must be relevant to their community themes (Zeng et al., 2009). Though most of online advertisers pay attention to branding, awareness, positioning, and informing a particular community, it is supposed that when members share the same social identity, they are more aware and have higher positive expectations toward perceiving relevance of advertisement content (Soares and Pinho 2014). Additionally, advertisers can take advantage of their knowledge about a certain part to design advertisement more appropriately. Therefore, advertisers will expand their advertisements not merely based on general features of a product but based on what matters to the person who receives and sees them. On the other hand, some studies have admitted the relationship between social identity, and perceiving the relevance of advertisements (Soares and Pinho 2014, Zeng et al. 2009). Accordingly, the seventh research hypothesis is as follows;

H7: there is a positive relationship between social identity and perceived advertisement relevance in online social networks.

When online community members have certain group intention to need to advertisement, they must be able to internalize this idea that advertisement is to the benefit of the whole community (Zeng et al., 2009). Hence, they value advertisement in that community more. Similarly, it is expected that perceived advertisement relevance contribute to higher value of cyber advertisements (Soares and Pinho 2014). As a consequence, the following research hypotheses are stated:

H8: there is a positive relationship between group intentions to accept advertising in online social networks and perceived advertisement relevance in online social networks.

H9: there is positive relationship between group intention to accept advertisement in online social networks and perceived value of advertisement in online social networks.

H10: there is positive relationship between perception of advertisement relevance in social sites and perceived value of advertisement in online social networks.

On the other hand, the effectiveness of cyber advertisement has constantly drawn the attention of marketing managers and academic community. Although most studies have focused on attitude toward online advertisements (Soares et al. 2012), behavioral scales such as brand awareness and the rate of clicking have also been evaluated. For example, studies have emphasized that advertisement relevance has a positive effect on clicking rate (Robinson et al. 2007). Similarly, previous studies have demonstrated that there is a positive correlation between advertisement value and attitude toward advertisement (Ducoffe, 1995, 1996). Considering the above stated analysis, the following hypotheses are stated:

H11: there is a positive relationship between perceived advertisement value in social sites and Response towards OSN advertisements.

H12: there is a positive relationship between perceived advertisement relevance and response towards OSN advertisements.

3. Research Methodology

The present research model is achieved based on data gathered from 340 questionnaires distributed among business management students of Tehran North branch of Islamic Azad University and it was analyzed by LISEREL software based on structural equations modeling. All respondents were member of at least one of the popular social networks. The aforementioned questionnaire was made up of three parts;

- 1) Explanations: In fact, the goal of data gathering and the necessity of respondents' cooperation for supplying essential data were elaborated in this part. To this end, the preciousness of data obtained

through questionnaire was highlighted so as to encourage respondents to reply honestly and appropriately.

- 2) Demographic questions: Four questions about education level, age, gender, and membership of social networks were embedded in this part. Table 1 shows the distribution of these features.
- 3) Questions related to research variables: This part consists of 33 questions. Six items measure perceived enjoyment (Moon and Kim 2001, Soares and Pinho 2014, Van der Heijden 2004). three items measured cognitive social identity, three items measured affective social identity, and four items measured evaluative social identity (Dholakia et al., 2004; Shen et al., 2011; Zhou, 2011), four items measured group norm (Soares and Pinho, 2014; Zeng et al., 2009), two items measured subjective norm (Taylor and Todd 1995, Zhou 2011), three items measured group intention to advertising (Soares and Pinho, 2014; Zeng et al., 2009), three items measured perceived advertisement relevance (Soares and Pinho, 2014; Zeng et al., 2009), three items measured perceived advertisement value (Soares and Pinho, 2014; Zeng et al., 2009), and three items measured response towards OSN advertisements (Ducoffe, 1995; Soares and Pinho, 2014; Zeng et al., 2009). Likert five rate scale was applied for designing this part.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n=340)

variable		Frequency	%	mode
Gender	male	194	57%	male
	female	146	43%	
Age	18-24	88	26%	25-34
	25-34	150	44%	
	35-44	36	11%	
	45-54	38	11%	
	Over 55	28	8%	
Level of Education	Diploma	36	11%	MA/MS students
	BA student	102	30%	
	MA/MS student	115	34%	
	Ph.D. student	80	24%	
membership of social networks	linkdin	77	23%	viber
	facebook	187	55%	
	instagram	216	64%	
	twitter	38	11%	
	viber	333	98%	
	whats app	244	72%	
	kik	53	16%	
	line	216	64%	
other social networks	90	26%		

4. Findings

Structural equation modeling was used to analyze the relationship between variables (Bagozzi and Yi 2012, Joreskog et al. 1979). In this regard, figure 2 shows the research model in standardized estimation situation and figure 3, shows the research model in t-value situation which is indicative of the relationship between observed variables (in rectangle , which is directly measured by the researcher) and latent variables (circles, which is inferred from correlations between measured variables). Accordingly, questions stated in appendix are indicative of model observed variables.

In structural equation modeling, coefficients are divided into two groups. The first group is measurement equations which are about the relationships between latent and observed variables. These equations are called loading factors. The second group is those structural equations which are about the relationships between latent and latent variables and are used for hypothesis testing. These coefficients are called path coefficient. Loading factors and path coefficients can be estimated. According to this model, path coefficient is significant at 95% level if t value is out of (+1.96 to -1.96) but if t value is within this range, path coefficient will not be significant. Path coefficient is significant at 99% level if t value is out of (+2.58 to -2.58).

PE=Perceived enjoyment, SI=Social identity, GN=Group norms, SN=Subjective norm, GITA=Group intentions towards advertising, PAR=Perceived advertisement relevance, PAV=Perceived advertisement value, RTA=Response towards OSN advertisements

Figure 2. The research model in standardized estimation situation

PE=Perceived enjoyment, SI=Social identity, GN=Group norms, SN=Subjective norm, GITA=Group intentions towards advertising, PAR=Perceived advertisement relevance, PAV=Perceived advertisement value, RTA=Response towards OSN advertisements

Figure 3. The research model in t-value situation

Confirmative factor analysis (CFA) was applied for analyzing construct validity. Confirmative factor analysis results are summarized in table 2. As depicted in the table, t-values indicate that all loadings are significant at 0.001. Therefore, the under study constructs enjoy good construct validity. Furthermore, all Cronbach's alpha values are over 0.7 which implies a good reliability (Cramer 1994).

Table 2. Loading Factors of Research Constructs

Factor	PE	SI	GN	SN	GITA	PAR	PAV	RTA	Cronbach's alpha
Item									
PE1	0.87**								0.92
PE2	0.72**								
PE3	0.81**								
PE4	0.91**								
PE5	0.89**								
PE6	0.69**								
SI1		0.88**							0.90
SI2		0.86**							
SI3		0.86**							
GN1			0.81**						0.88
GN2			0.80**						
GN3			0.77**						
GN4			0.91**						
SN1				0.68**					0.70
SN2				0.79**					
GITA1					0.80**				0.82

GITA2					0.84**				
GITA3					0.72**				
PAR1						0.82**			0.87
PAR2						0.88**			
PAR3						0.81**			
PAV1							0.64**		0.78
PAV2							0.80**		
PAV3							0.80**		
RTA1								0.73**	0.71
RTA2								0.68**	
RTA3								0.63**	
Notes: **p < 0.01									

Generally, in structural equation modeling, model's goodness of fit is not interpreted merely based on individual indexes. In fact, all indexes must be interpreted together. Table 3 lists the recommended (Hair 2010), and actual values of some fit indexes. As shown in the table, the various indexes used show that the fit of the saturated model is good.

Table 3. The model's goodness of fit indices

indexes	chi ² /df	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	NNFI	RMSEA
Recommended value	> 3	> 0.90	> 0.80	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	< 0.08
Actual value	2.88	0.90	0.82	0.95	0.93	0.95	0.075
Notes:							
chi ² /df is the ratio between Chi-square and degrees of freedom, GFI is Goodness of Fit Index, AGFI is the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index, CFI is the Comparative Fit Index, NFI is the Normed Fit Index, NNFI is the Non-Normed Fit Index, RMSEA is Root Mean Square Error of Approximation							

According to the results of path coefficient and t value, which are demonstrated in figure 2 and 3 and table 4, at 99% significance level, there is positive and significant relationship between perceived enjoyment and subjective norm ($\gamma=0.66$, $t=8.60$), between perceived enjoyment and group norm ($\gamma=0.12$, $t=2.09$), and between perceived enjoyment and social identity ($\gamma=0.33$, $t=5.70$). As well, results indicate a positive relationship between subjective norm and group intention toward advertisement in OSN ($\beta=0.17$, $t=3.08$), between group norm and group intention to advertising in OSN ($\beta=0.23$, $t= 4.62$), and between social identity and group intention toward advertising in OSN ($\beta=0.61$, $t=10.48$). On the other hand, according to outcomes, there is positive and significant relationship between social identity and perceived advertisement relevance ($\beta=0.41$, $t=6.27$). besides, a positive relationship between group intention toward advertising in OSN and perceived advertisement relevance in OSN ($\beta=0.45$, $t=6.52$), positive relationship between group intention toward advertising in OSN and perceived advertisement value in OSN ($\beta=0.29$, $t=3.02$), and also a positive relationship between perceived advertisement relevance in OSN and perceived advertisement value in OSN ($\beta=0.31$, $t=3.27$) were confirmed. Ultimately, according to results, there is positive and significant relationship between perceived advertisement value and response toward advertising in OSN ($\beta=0.41$, $t=5.41$) and between perceived advertisement relevance in OSN and response toward advertisement ($\beta=0.51$, $t=7.22$).

Table 4. Summary of Hypotheses Tests

Research hypothesis	Hypothesis (direction)	Path coefficient	t-value	Significance	The result of research hypothesis
H1	PE → SI (+)	0.33	5.70	p < 0.01	supported
H2	PE → GN (+)	0.12	2.09	p < 0.05	supported
H3	PE → SN (+)	0.66	8.60	p < 0.01	supported
H4	SN → GITA (+)	0.17	3.08	p < 0.01	supported
H5	GN → GITA (+)	0.23	4.62	p < 0.01	supported
H6	SI → GITA (+)	0.61	10.48	p < 0.01	supported
H7	SI → PAR (+)	0.41	6.27	p < 0.01	supported
H8	GITA → PAR (+)	0.45	6.52	p < 0.01	supported
H9	GITA → PAV (+)	0.29	3.02	p < 0.01	supported
H10	PAR → PAV (+)	0.31	3.27	p < 0.01	supported
H11	PAR → RTA (+)	0.51	7.22	p < 0.01	supported
H12	PAV → RTA (+)	0.41	5.41	p < 0.01	supported

Notes:

PE=Perceived enjoyment, SI=Social identity, GN=Group norms, SN=Subjective norm, GITA=Group intentions towards advertising, PAR=Perceived advertisement relevance, PAV=Perceived advertisement value, RTA=Response towards OSN advertisements

5. Result and Discussion

The present study pinpointed the factors affecting online social networks users' response to advertisement. In this regard, it was analyzed how perceived enjoyment impacts on social influence variables including social identity, group norm, and subjective norm and how social influence variables affect on advertisement relevant variables including intention to advertising in OSN , perceived advertisement relevance, and perceived advertisement value. According to data gathered from 340 business management students and applying structural equation modeling, all of hypotheses were supported (table 4).

In this regard, hypothesis 1, 2, and 3 considering the relationship between perceived enjoyment and social influence variables were all supported. This outcome is in line with Soares and Pinho (2014). Accordingly, perceived enjoyment of OSNs can be regarded as a key factor in forming common individual and group identity and one's commitment to group goals and norms. Besides, it was found that when people attend in a virtual community and feel attached and belonged to it, kind of common feeling grows among group members that can result in group intentions. This finding agrees with some of previous studies (Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2002; Soares and Pinho, 2014; Zeng et al., 2009). It is inferred that social influence variables play critical role in understanding consumers' conduct of using virtual social networks. It was also demonstrated that social identity impacts positively not only upon group intention toward advertising but also upon perceived advertisement relevance. This result accords with Zeng et al., (2009) and also Soares and Pinho (2014). As well, positive and significant relationship between perceived advertisement relevance and perceived advertisement value were confirmed. This is also in line with some previous studies (Soares et al., 2012; Zeng et al., 2009).

There were some limitations in present research. First, merely business management students were samples. As a matter of fact, these students in comparison with others who lack enough knowledge about marketing communications have more positive attitude toward advertising. On the other hand, most of participants of present research were youngsters; whereas, other group ranges are increasingly taking interest in using OSNs. Therefore, research results will not be easily generalized. Nevertheless, present research was an attempt to reach

to a more precise recognition of consumer conducts in online social networks and it tried to study hedonic aspect of using online social networks. It was tried to recognize how group dynamics are reinforced between members of online social networks and helps to generation of an attitude toward advertising. This fact can bring about widespread practical results for marketing managers.

6. References

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